

Nonoscillation Criteria for Nonlinear Delay Dynamic Systems on Time Scales

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Abstract : In this paper, we consider the nonlinear delay dynamic system $x^{\Delta}(t)=p(t)f_1(y(t)), y^{\Delta}(t)=-q(t)f_2(x(t-\tau))$. We establish some necessary and sufficient conditions for the existence of nonoscillatory solutions with special asymptotic properties for the system. We generalize the known results in the literature. One example is included to illustrate the results

Keywords : dynamic system; oscillation; time scales; two-dimensional

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